

THE EARLY PHASES OF THE FOIE GRAS INDUSTRY IN SOUTH-WEST FRANCE (C. 1780-1955): A CONTRIBUTION TO THE HISTORY OF FOOD INNOVATION

*Las primeras fases de la industria del foie-gras
en el sudoeste de Francia (c. 1780-1955).
Una contribución a la historia de la innovación alimentaria*

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Resumen

El foie-gras que se consume en la actualidad es un producto reciente. Nació en el sudoeste de Francia durante el siglo XVIII gracias al desarrollo del cultivo de maíz y de la crianza de dos patos: el pato almizclero (*Cairina moschata*) y, sobre todo, el pato mulo (*Cairina moschata x Anas platyrhynchos*). Este ensayo subraya la adaptación de los actores involucrados en la transformación del foie-gras a los cambios tecnológicos, desde la aparición del foie-gras moderno hasta los años 1950 —período en el cual se inventó el bloque de foie-gras. Este análisis muestra que la innovación es la tradición de la industria del foie gras desde sus orígenes.

Palabras claves: innovación, agroindustria, pato, ganso, foie-gras, France

Abstract

The foie gras that is currently consumed is a recent product. It was born in the South-West France during the 18th century, thanks to the development of maize growing and of two ducks breeding: the Muscovy duck (*Cairina moschata*) and, mostly, the mule duck (*Cairina moschata x Anas platyrhynchos*). This essay underlines the adaptation of the actors involved in the foie gras processing to changing technological environment from the birth of modern foie gras to the 1950s —time when the foie gras block has been invented. This analyzes shows that innovation is the tradition of the foie gras industry from its beginnings.

Key words: innovation, agro-industry, duck, goose, foie gras, France

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In the early twenty-first century, the supremacy of South-West France on the world market of force-fed palmiped livers is clearly established. In 2009, this region produced more than 55% of the 25, 500 tons of foie gras to the world.¹ Furthermore, the two-world leader companies in the field of the production, transformation, and marketing of foie gras were located in this area: Euralis-Rougié (Lescar, Pyrénées-Atlantiques) and Maisadour-Delpeyrat (Haut-Maco, Landes). An extreme rationalization and integration of the regional foie gras industry makes possible the current production levels —around 20 million of ducks are bred, killed and processed each year. This industrialization process is recent and corresponds to the latest phase of foie gras sector that started in the 1970s-1980s. Nevertheless, it can be considered as an evolution perfectly in line with the tradition of innovation that characterized the South-West France foie gras industry from its origins. In this text, we will actually consider the early historical phases of the regional foie gras sector —that means a period that began in the late eighteenth-century with the first real developments of the commercial production of duck liver pies and ended with the invention of the liver block [*bloc de foie gras*] in the middle of the 1950s.

During this period, the South-West France foie gras industry grew assimilating innovations and using new transport systems to obtain its perishable raw material or to gain new markets and customers throughout the world easier. Logically, these first phases of the foie gras industry were also a time during which more or less successful firms specialized in fattened liver processing were founded. Prior to discussing these technological and capitalistic aspects of regional foie gras history, it is necessary to examine certain features of the foie gras that was processed by the industry. Foie gras processing is one of the latest step of a long agri-alimentary chain.

1. THE BIRTH OF THE MODERN FOIE GRAS

The gastronomic discourse accustomed us to thinking the foie gras was born in Ancient Egypt. Nevertheless, it is necessary for fully understanding the foie gras phenomenon to forget this popular opinion founded on a

1. Statistics from CIFOG & French Ministry of Agriculture. Since 2000, the South-West France that produces foie gras can be practically identified with the area where foie gras is produced within the framework of the Protected Geographical Indication *Canard à foie gras du Sud-Ouest*: Aquitaine, Midi-Pyrénées, Corrèze and certain cantons of Haute-Vienne and Aude.

reading of the past that totally tramples underfoot the scientific definition of the historical continuity.² In fact, properly simplifying, two different and disconnected traditions of foie gras production can be identified. The oldest one blossomed in the Roman Empire and lived on certain regions of Italy and Eastern Europe, especially in Jewish communities. The other one was born in the South-West France in the early modern times after the arrival of the Muscovy duck (*Cairina moschata*) in the local poultry yards and the integration of the maize (*Zea mays*) in the local agri-systems. The changes produced by these introductions were subtle and progressive. At least from the end of the sixteenth century, the crossing between Muscovy ducks and common female ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*) produced a sterile hybrid duck with quite good ability to get fat: the *canard mulard* [mule duck] (Figure 1). From the seventeenth century, for its part, the maize slowly started to take the place of the millets (*Panicum miliaceum*, *Setaria italica*) in the troughs used to fatten palmipeds in accordance with the local traditional method. This substitution, which was a real nutritional revolution, created necessary conditions for the chancy development of real fattened livers in South-West France (Figure 2). In the course of the second half of the eighteenth century, the generalization of force-feeding [*gavage*] allowed a regular production of goose and duck foie gras in certain parts of this region. If Alsace, Venetia and other European areas also produced goose liver using other methods in this time, South-West France was the only part of the world where foie gras was obtained from ducks—the main part from mule ducks and the rest from Muscovy ones. This monopoly was still true until the second half of the twentieth century.³

When the production of foie gras became regular, the French elites enjoyed fat and tender meat products. As a result, this food was immediately regarded as a delicacy that was in good taste to serve on the most sophisticated tables. In 1788, for instance, Louis-Sébastien Mercier mentioned the fat liver pies of Toulouse among the prestigious dishes that the exigent Parisian gourmets appreciated.⁴ This gastronomic recognition had economical effects: the foie gras quickly joined the category of the

2. Bronislaw Malinowski, *A Scientific Theory of Culture and others Essays* (1944), Chapel Hill, The University of North Carolina Press, 1973, p. 20.

3. It is not possible to mention here in detail these themes that require a complex biocultural approach, you can find more information in Frédéric Duhart, *De confits en foies gras. Une histoire des oies et des canards du Sud-Ouest*, San Sebastian/Bayonne, Elkar, 2009.

4. Louis-Sébastien Mercier, *Le Tableau de Paris*, Amsterdam, 1788, pp. 345-346.

high value goods that were better to sell than to eat for the modest rural households. In the late eighteenth century this supply of foie gras was strictly limited to the winter months because of constraints that followed from the seasonality of palmiped laying, the cycle of maize production and the necessity of processing the preserved meat [*confit*] under low temperatures. The foie gras production remained a cold time activity during the rest of the period under consideration. Nevertheless, the foie gras industry was more dependent of climatic conditions in its first phase than after the spreading of Appert's methods: its main products were quickly perishable pies and terrines that could only circulate when the atmosphere was suitable.

Figure 1. Mule ducks (ancient type)

In the course of its phase of emergence, the foie gras pâté processing was mainly practised as a seasonal activity by urban pastry cooks and caterers. Duck and goose livers were just a prestigious ingredient. At the end of the eighteenth century, terrines made with fattened liver were just examples of the numerous products that Mr Noel prepared in his workshop located in Angoulême. His main activity was the elaboration of pâtés with turkey meat, partridges and hares. Foie gras, like thrushes

or skylarks, represented for him a more occasional ingredient because its calendar of availability.⁵ However, some of the craftsmen interested in foie gras processing soon considered and promoted their pâtés as their unique or principal speciality. On December 22nd 1790, for example, the paper *Les Affiches de Toulouse* published an advertisement for a local cook who prepared on request all size duck liver pâtés.⁶

Figure 2. Force-fed duck livers

In this time, foie gras could logically be processed in all the parts of the South-West France where ducks and geese were force-fed in their immediate vicinity. As the activity of Mr. Noel and others suggest, it is probable that foie gras pâtés were elaborated by craftsmen located in Perigord from the last eighteenth century —even if the terrine that made the gastronomic renown of this region at this period was made with partridges and truffles.⁷ While the fattened liver processing was a discreet activity in certain areas, the region around Toulouse became the first centre of foie gras industry clearly identified in the South-West France. Denis Diderot mentioned the pâtés sent from this town in the 1770's. Few decades later, Alexandre Balthazar Grimod de la Reynière recalled that the

5. Giacomo Girolamo Casanova, *Mémoires* (1789-1798), Paris, Garnier, 1880, t. 7, p. 371

6. *Les Affiches de Toulouse*, 22/12/1790.

7. Frédéric Duhart, *De confits en foies gras...*, San Sebastian/Bayonne, Elkar, 2009, pp. 314-317.

pâtés from Agen and Auch were also famous in Paris. Indeed, if a part of the pâtés made in the vicinity of Toulouse was consumed by the local elite, another was exported to the gourmets as far as allowed by this delicacy perishability and the winter temperatures.⁸

As the fresh fattened liver is a very fragile raw material, foie gras pâté processing actors were totally dependent on a local offer in a period where the time distances were frequently still long in the South-West France. Conversely, the fattened liver producers had to obtain the highest possible benefit on a market where the demand was restricted. The most notable consequence of this situation was the start of a complex quality pursuit. From at least the first decade of the nineteenth century, for instance, the exigencies of the pastry cooks led the peasants located in the vicinity of Toulouse to make it possible to obtain firm duck livers.⁹ As the craftsmen attached a secondary importance to goose liver, the search of quality in the case of this food was not orientated towards a similar technological ideal. According to classical popular representations of the «good product», peasants looked for the production of the big goose livers as possible mainly through the selection of their breeder birds.

2. EMERGENCE AND CONSOLIDATION OF A MODERN FOIE GRAS INDUSTRY

At the end of the first quarter of the nineteenth century, the production of foie gras terrines and pies was a well-established activity in two areas of the South-West of France: the part of the Gascony close to Toulouse and the Perigord where familial firms interested in the palmiped liver processing opened their doors in the course of the 1810s-1820s —Lasalvetat (Perigueux, 1810), Massoulié & Richard (Sarlat, 1812), Bizac (Sarlat, 1825),¹⁰ etc. A lot of these establishments were also interested in truffle trade because their geographical situation. Consequently, some of their owners were soon attentive to the possibilities for long preserving food that the method of

8. Denis Diderot, *Œuvres complètes* (1743-1782), Paris, Garnier, 1875, t. 6, p. 306; Alexandre-Balthazar Grimod de la Reynière, *Almanach des gourmands*, Paris, Maradan, 1804, p. 73, 1805, p. 250 et 1807, p. 308.

9. Philippe Isidore Picot de Lapeyrouse, «Topographie rurale du canton de Montastruc, département de la Haute-Garonne», *Mémoires d'Agriculture publiés par la Société Royale et Centrale d'Agriculture*, 1814, p. 123.

10. Silvano Serventi, *La grande histoire du foie gras*, Paris, Flammarion, 1993, p. 86.

sterilization promoted by Nicolas Appert offered.¹¹ This technique was used to preserve foie gras in workshops located in Périgord from at least the end of the first third of the nineteenth century. This innovation considerably extended the market area for the local pâté. In the early 1830s, small quantities of *Pâté de foie gras de Périgord* were regularly brought to Calcutta by ships from Bordeaux!¹² On the French market, the foie gras processed in Périgord became more accessible, visible and famous with as result a progressive but finally strong identification of this region with this food.¹³

In the course of the following decades, the foie gras processing activity expanded in other parts of South-West France according to different industrial and commercial strategies. The association of fattened liver and truffle transformations remained a classical model of functioning in Périgord and Quercy. For instance, Rougié (Souillac, Lot) never abandoned the truffle trade despite a remarkable development in the field of foie gras processing. A clear specialization in palmiped product processing characterized the major part of the firms founded in the heart of Gascony: Sarrade (Eauze, Gers, 1850), Sansoube (Dax, Landes, 1870), Leymarie (Hagetmau, Landes, 1890), Dubarry (Gimont, Gers, 1908), Durocher (Mont-de-Marsan, Landes, 1919),¹⁴ etc. Opposite, the canning factories located in the vicinity of the port of Bordeaux processed the foie gras at the same time than a lot of other foods. In 1904, for example, Duprat & Durand tined foie gras, green peas, French beans, tomatoes, fishes or tripe in its shops located in Talence.¹⁵ In Toulouse, where the importance of the foie gras industry became relatively low in the course of the nineteenth century, the pâté making was widely still practised in combination with others activities. Tivolier, which produced famous foie gras between the end of the 1850's and the middle of the 1920's, was a restaurant and catering firm.¹⁶

11. Nicolas Appert, *Le livre de tous les ménages ou l'art de conserver pendant plusieurs années*, Paris, Patris, 1810.

12. Victor Jacquemont, *Correspondance avec sa famille et plusieurs de ses amis pendant son voyage en Inde*, Bruxelles, Dumont, 1836, t. 1, p. 164.

13. Frédéric Duhart, «L'émergence d'un terroir gourmand: le Périgord dans le discours culinaire et gastronomique (xviii^e siècle-début du xx^e siècle)», *Bulletin de la Société Historique et Archéologique du Périgord*, 131, 2004, pp. 66-67.

14. René Cuzacq, «Autour du foie gras des Landes», *Bulletin de la Société de Borda*, 68, 1954, p. 178.

15. *Bulletin de l'Épicerie et du commerce*, 12/1904.

16. Pierre Gérard & Claude Monteil, *Célébration de l'oie des archives à l'assiette*, Toulouse, Arch. départementales de la Haute-Garonne, 1993, pp. 119-120.

Perigord constituted the principal centre of foie gras transformation in South-West France throughout the first half of the twentieth century. In 1903, Victor Eugène Ardouin Dumazet calculated that the factories located in the Périgoueix area processed a third of the total quantity of foie gras processed each year in the whole South-West France.¹⁷ Five decades later, Périgord was still the undisputed leader in this activity. It was also the only place where important processing plants were established. In the rest of the region, small-scale units were the rule. En 1954, for instance, the six foie gras factories that stayed open in Toulouse barely employed fifty two persons.¹⁸ During this period, the firms located in Périgord did not use only raw material produced in their immediate vicinity. Indeed, innovations in the field of transport radically changed the organization of the foie gras trade from the second half of the nineteenth century. When the development of the railways allowed sending fresh fattened livers far away from the markets where they had been brought by the peasants, a new professional group became an essential link of the foie gras production chain: the brokers [courtiers] or senders [expéditeurs]. They took care of buying good livers then sending them as soon as possible to their customers: canning factories, restaurants,¹⁹ etc. Thanks to their action, the firms that processed foie gras could become less dependent on the strictly local offer in terms of quantity and quality. In the early 1880's, Tivollier obtained goose livers from six different brokers. Twenty five years later, this firm received foie gras from senders located in Gramat (Lot, distance to Toulouse: around 160 km), in Dax (Landes, distance to Toulouse: around 230 km), etc. Such extended supply area allowed to have special quality exigencies that would have been difficult to maintain front of a restricted offer. When it was time to prepare its finest pâtés, for instance, Tivollier could exclusively order «male duck livers» with the certitude to obtain them in sufficient quantity.²⁰

The senders did not exclusively work for South-West France factories. Thanks to the railway, fresh duck livers started to be dispatched to restaurant owners established in Paris and other majors towns during the second half of the nineteenth century. After the First World War,

17. Victor Eugène Ardouin-Dumazet, *Voyage en France: Bordelais et Périgord* (29), Paris, Berger-Levrault, 1903, p. 272.

18. Jean Coppolani, *Toulouse. Étude de géographie urbaine*, Toulouse, Privat, 1954, p. 223.

19. Victor Eugène Ardouin-Dumazet, *Voyage en France: Gascogne* (30), Paris, Berger-Levrault, 1903, p. 265; Robert Labeyrie, *L'ambassadeur du Sud-Ouest. Mon itinéraire gourmand*, Paris, Publibook, 2004, pp. 35-41.

20. Arch. dép. Haute-Garonne, 8 J 663-664, 1880-1904.

brokers located in South-West France became important suppliers of goose livers for Alsatian factories. These firms particularly paid attention to the technological quality of the raw material they bought. They soon remarked that the big goose livers from South-West France frequently released too much fat when they were cooked to produce first quality canned pâtés. Some of the Alsatian factories decided to order again better goose livers from Eastern producers as soon it was possible. This situation helped the South-West factory heads realizing the necessity of being more demanding on goose liver quality. As they were not used to import raw material, they looked for a local solution. From the end of the 1940's, they supported an ambitious program of genetic improvement of the local goose populations. Concretely, in 1949, they founded the experimental station of Artiguères (Benquet, Landes) where a goose whose liver present a better technological quality than the majority of traditional local population ones was obtained in the early 1960s.²¹

Figure 3. Foie gras factory Segou, early 20th century

21. Frédéric Duhart, *De confits en foies gras...*, San Sebastian/Bayonne, Elkar, 2009, pp. 33-37.

This action reminds us that the foie gras industry classically looks after innovation. During the period under consideration, numerous factories proudly mentioned their modernity in their commercial material. In the early twentieth century, Daburon Frères notepaper showed an exterior view of a model factory with a smoky chimney. For its part, the factory owned by the family Ségu in Cazères (Haute-Garonne) became a postcard theme (Figure 3). In 1931, an advertisement for Foie Gras Lalanne (Aire-sur-l'Adour, Landes) specified that its factory was «continually modernized», etc.

The foie gras industry taste for innovation clearly appears through the constant diversification of the range of products commercialized from the time when the Appert's method of preservation was adopted. This offer was early characterized by an accumulation principle. Generally, the new product did not take the place of a precedent one. It came to complete preexistent range opening new perspectives for sale and consumption. In 1877, for instance, Rilhac (Brive-la-Gaillarde, Corrèze) proposed its customers canned foie gras pâtés, but also old-fashioned way terrines or pies.²² Some firms used all the resources offered by the tin packaging to develop a range of new products in perfect appropriateness to the practices and aspirations of the modern elite. In 1896, Rœdel (Bordeaux, Gironde) proposed a classical foie gras pâté garnished with truffles canned in little tin within its range called «Canned foods for tourists» [conserves pour touristes].²³ Canning did not only allow preserving much more time the foie gras pâté and sending it during all seasons far away from the factories, also made commercially relevant another product: the liver just cooked in its own fat inside the tin [foie gras au naturel]. This product was appreciated in restaurants and gourmet houses throughout the world because it gave the liberty of cooking foie gras where obtaining fresh fattened liver was impossible—for instance, in San Francisco at the beginning of the twentieth century.²⁴ The preparation of such canned pâtés and foies gras au naturel was a perfect way to make profit with top-quality livers. Of course, it was possible to use lower quality livers to obtain standard products. But, they were much less profitable. At the end of the 1890's, the price of the top quality foie gras pâté produced by Bouton

22. *Revue des vins et des liqueurs et des produits pour l'exportation*, 04/1877.

23. *Le Gourmet*, 10 /1896.

24. Victor Hirtzler, *Hotel St. Francis Cook Book*, Chicago, The Hotel Monthly Press, 1919. p. 216.

(Perigueux, Dordogne) was one-third higher than the price of the second-quality one!²⁵ Consequently, the firms that processed palmiped livers also considered innovation as a way to make more profit with the raw material they could not use to prepare extra-quality classical products. A lot of firms adopted the solution that consisted in elaborating purées with foie gras and frequently other ingredients. Even if they were less expensive, these products were still delicacies mainly intended for high-class consumers. As the foie gras for sandwiches that Lajaunie & Lafon (Eymet, Dordogne) sold in the early 1930s reminds, they were designed to be associated with a certain type of modern society events: luncheons, etc.

In 1954, La Comtesse du Barry (Gimont, Gers) added a recently invented product to its range of fattened liver preparations: the foie gras block [bloc de foie gras]. Homogeneous and tasty, it was an emulsion of foie gras and water. Of course, it was different from the classical «entire foie gras». But it was an unmixed and authentic foie gras quite different of the purees, creams and other products elaborated until then. The management of different firms soon understood that the block was a profitable innovation with a strong commercial potential. In 1957, it was already included in the ranges of foie gras elaborated in many factories in Landes, Haute-Garonne,²⁶ etc. This integration of the block fabrication in the ordinary practices of the regional foie gras industry corresponded to the entry into a new phase of its history —a time characterized by a notable intensification of its activity and a relative democratization of the foie gras consumption.

3. CONCLUSION

The strong tradition of innovation is certainly one of the most characteristic aspects of the foie gras industry in South-West France during the period under consideration in this text. It was born as an adaptation of the classical pastry cookery to an innovator raw material. It knew its first notable development when it adopted an innovator preservation method. It became a more geographically polarized activity benefiting from the development of innovator transportation ways. Furthermore, the foie gras industry regularly completed and renewed its range of products

25. *Revue des vins et liqueurs et des produits alimentaires pour l'exportation*, 02/1899.

26. Comtesse Du Barry, 1908-2008. *Un siècle de gastronomie sans cesse revisitée*, Établissements C.S.L., *Catalogue*, 1957, p. 143-144.

with innovator preparations! Of course, such tradition of innovation can be also identified in the case of various European food industries. But, the example offered by South-West France foie gras industry represents undoubtedly one of the most perfect examples of this kind of dynamics we can find.

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